

Incidence of crown sheath rot disease in rice in West Bengal.

presence of *Gaeumannomyces graminis* var. *graminis*, characterized by hyphae with distinct hyphopodia and beaked perithecia that produced unitunicate asci with eight long, curved ascospores. □

Nitrogen level, cultivar, and *R. solani* isolate effect on sheath blight (ShB) development

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Eight rice varieties differing in duration, plant height, and ShB susceptibility were grown in 30-cm-diam pots in the greenhouse with 2 N levels: 1.6 g and 3.2 g/pot. N was applied in 2 equal splits at 21 d after transplanting and at panicle initiation. Staggered planting synchronized booting.

Ten isolates of *R. solani* differing in growth rate, sclerotia production, and culture type were selected from 98 isolates collected from rice, grass, millet, maize, water hyacinth, and weeds. Plants were inoculated at booting with inocula prepared in a rice hull:rice grain medium. About 100 ml of the inocula was placed between tillers. Inoculated plants were covered with polyethylene sheets at night.

Lesion height/plant height was recorded at 5d intervals. The ratios of

leaf to sheath area infection were compared 28 d after inoculation.

Development of relative lesion height (RLH) and percent area infected (PAI) by isolates of *R. solani* differed among varieties. The influence of N level was apparent only at later stages of lesion

development. However, there was an isolate × N interaction.

Isolate RS72-1 produced the lowest RLH as well as PAI in all varieties and was the least virulent isolate tested (Fig. 1,2). The other isolates developed higher RLH and PAI in IR58 and

1. Vertical development of ShB in IR58 by different isolates of *R. solani* at 2 N levels. IRRI, 1987.

2. Vertical development of ShB in IR64 by different isolates of *R. solani* at 2 N levels. IRRI, 1987.

IR1317 (short varieties) than in Narnpungbyeo, Ta-poo-cho-z, and IR26 (tall varieties). The results suggest that,

in addition to other factors, ShB development will be influenced by the virulence of the pathogen isolate. □

Bacterial blight (BB) in hilly regions of Nepal

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BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama, 1922) Dye was first observed in the terai region with the introduction of high-yielding rice varieties. Taichung Native 1 was the first

victim. Later, improved varieties IR5, Jaya, Padma, and IR24, and some local varieties were infected. This disease has been confined to hilly regions.

In a disease survey in Sep 1986, BB symptoms were observed in the Sorakhutte, Nayabazar, and Mhaipi areas (altitude about 1,238 m) of Kathmandu valley. Blighted specimens were tested in the laboratory and BB was confirmed. The disease was found in Himali, Purple, Khumal-3, and

Taichung 176 varieties. Himali and Purple were heavily infected. Infection was uniform and distributed throughout the plots. Aggregate infected area was about 1.5 ha. Although infection was severe and uniform, grain filling was not much affected, maybe because it was a late foliar infection.

The combination of rainy weather, strong winds, and moderate temperatures in Kathmandu favored rapid disease spread. Maximum and minimum temperatures Jun-Oct were 28 °C and 19 °C. Total rainfall was 1,040 mm in 87 d.

BB also was found in the western hilly regions: Khurkot, Armadi, and Shibalaya Panchayat in Parbat district; Kalika and Mulpani Panchayat, including Baglung Bazar, in Baglung district, and Ratnechour Panchayat in Myagdi district. Local varieties Gudura, Gauriwa, Jarneli, Aanadi, Aagani, and Panhela, and improved varieties Masuli and Khumal 3 were infected. Most of the incidences were in river basin areas (774 m) up to the mid-range of hills (1,084 m). Infection was mostly in shaded areas. □

Relationship between growth rate, sclerotia production, and virulence of isolates of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn

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Cultures of *Rhizoctonia solani* causing sheath blight were isolated from diseased specimens of rice, grass, weeds, water hyacinth, maize, and millet from fields on the IRRI farm and in Laguna Province, Philippines. Growth rate (regression coefficient), sclerotia production (no./plate in 10 d), and cultural characteristics of 98 isolates were studied using potato dextrose agar-(PDA) medium enriched with 0.1% urea.

Virulence of 10 isolates representing different culture types, growth rate, and sclerotia production were tested on IR58